

Package ‘ram’

October 21, 2025

Type Package

Title Resource Allocation Models for Agro-Pastoral Systems

Version 0.0.0.9001

Description Tools to define and solve resource allocation models (RAM) for agro-pastoral systems.

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Imports dplyr,
plotly,
shiny (>= 1.5.0),
DT,
golem,
lpSolve,
config,
bslib,
openxlsx

Roxygen list(markdown = TRUE)

RoxygenNote 7.3.3

Suggests knitr,
ggplot2,
readxl,
rmarkdown,
htmltools,
testthat,
pkgdown

Encoding UTF-8

VignetteBuilder knitr

Config/testthat/edition 3

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app_server	<i>The application server-side</i>
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Description

The application server-side

Usage

```
app_server(input, output, session)
```

Arguments

input, output, session

Internal parameters for shiny. DO NOT REMOVE.

app_ui	<i>The application User-Interface</i>
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Description

The application User-Interface

Usage

```
app_ui(request)
```

create_ram_model	<i>Create a RAM Model</i>
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Description

Combines resources and activities into a RAM model object.

Usage

```
create_ram_model(resources, activities)
```

Arguments

resources	Data frame from define_resources().
activities	Data frame from define_activities().

Value

List of class 'ram_model'.

define_activities	<i>Define Activities</i>
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Description

Creates a data frame describing each activity, using resource names for columns.

Usage

```
define_activities(activities, activity_requirements_matrix, objective)
```

Arguments

activities	Character vector of activity names.
activity_requirements_matrix	Numeric matrix (resources x activities) of resource usage per activity. Row names must be resource names.
objective	Numeric vector of objective function coefficient per activity (e.g., profit for maximization, cost for minimization).

Value

Data frame with one row per activity, columns for each resource (named), and an objective column.

define_resources	<i>Define Resource Constraints</i>
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Description

Creates a data frame of resource constraints for the RAM model, allowing both upper (" \leq ") and lower (" \geq ") bounds.

Usage

```
define_resources(resources, availability, direction)
```

Arguments

resources	Character vector of constraint/resource names (e.g., "land", "labor", "protein_min").
availability	Numeric vector of right-hand sides (amounts available or required).
direction	Character vector of constraint directions; each value must be either " \leq " or " \geq ".

Value

Data frame with columns: resource, availability, and direction.

Examples

```
# Upper bounds only
define_resources(
  resources = c("land", "labor"),
  availability = c(100, 200),
  direction = c("<=", "<=")
)

# Mixed upper/lower bounds (min requirement for protein, max for feed)
define_resources(
  resources = c("protein_min", "feed_max"),
  availability = c(2.5, 10),
  direction = c(">=", "<=")
)
```

get_extdata	<i>Get Path to Extdata File</i>
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Description

Returns the installed path to a file bundled in inst/extdata.

Usage

```
get_extdata(filename, mustWork = TRUE)
```

Arguments

filename	Name of file under inst/extdata
mustWork	Logical; if TRUE throws error if not found

Value

Full path to the installed extdata file

namespace-overrides	<i>Namespace Overrides for DT - Shiny</i>
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Description

We want to use DT's versions of the table-output functions, not shiny's. This tells R to import all of shiny except those.

plot_ram	<i>Plot RAM Model Solution (plotly version)</i>
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Description

Visualizes the optimal allocation (activities) as an interactive barplot.

Usage

```
plot_ram(solution)
```

Arguments

solution	List returned by solve_ram().
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ram_optimize	<i>Optimize a Resource Allocation Model</i>
--------------	---

Description

Solves a linear programming model for resource allocation in agro-pastoral systems.

Usage

```
ram_optimize(profit, resource_use, availability)
```

Arguments

profit	Numeric vector. Profit (or objective coefficient) for each activity.
resource_use	Matrix. Rows = resources, Columns = activities. Each entry gives the use of resource per activity unit.
availability	Numeric vector. Total available amount for each resource (must match number of rows in resource_use).

Value

A list with:

optimal_activities	Named vector of optimal activity levels
max_profit	Optimal value of the objective function
status	Status code from lpSolve (0 = success)

Examples

```
profit <- c(20, 25)
resource_use <- matrix(c(1, 2, 2, 3, 3, 0), nrow = 3, byrow = TRUE)
rownames(resource_use) <- c("land", "labor", "feed")
colnames(resource_use) <- c("grazing", "haymaking")
availability <- c(100, 200, 300)
names(availability) <- rownames(resource_use)
ram_optimize(profit, resource_use, availability)
```

run_app	<i>Launch the RAM app in specified mode ("solve" or "builder")</i>
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Description

Launch the RAM app in specified mode ("solve" or "builder")

Usage

```
run_app(mode = c("solve", "builder"), ...)
```

Arguments

mode	Character, one of "solve" or "builder" (default: "solve")
...	Additional golem options

run_app_builder	<i>Launch the RAM app in builder mode</i>
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Description

Launch the RAM app in builder mode

Usage

```
run_app_builder(...)
```

Arguments

...	Additional golem options passed to the app
-----	--

run_app_solve	<i>Launch the RAM app in solver mode</i>
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Description

Launch the RAM app in solver mode

Usage

```
run_app_solve(...)
```

Arguments

...	Additional golem options passed to the app (via <code>get_golem_options()</code>)
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run_scenarios	<i>Run a batch of resource-allocation scenarios</i>
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Description

Run a batch of resource-allocation scenarios

Usage

```
run_scenarios(res_def, act_def, scenario_list, direction = "max")
```

Arguments

res_def	A resources spec as returned by define_resources()
act_def	An activities spec as returned by define_activities()
scenario_list	A named list of vectors; each vector are the alternative values for one resource (names must match res_def\$resource)
direction	"max" or "min"

Value

A data.frame with one row per scenario, the scenario inputs, the achieved objective, and one column per activity giving the optimal level of that activity.

sensitivity_ram	<i>Sensitivity Analysis for RAM (from solution object)</i>
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Description

Sensitivity Analysis for RAM (from solution object)

Usage

```
sensitivity_ram(solution)
```

Arguments

solution	List returned by solve_ram().
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Value

Data frame: resource, direction, availability, shadow_price, lower/upper bounds

 solve_ram

Solve a Resource Allocation Model with Mixed Constraints

Description

Solve a Resource Allocation Model with Mixed Constraints

Usage

```
solve_ram(model, direction = "max")
```

Arguments

model	A 'ram_model' object as returned by create_ram_model().
direction	"max" to maximize the objective, "min" to minimize (default: "max").

Value

A list with:

optimal_activities	Named vector of optimal activity levels
objective_value	Optimal value of the objective function
status	Status code from lpSolve (0 = success)

 summary_ram

Summary Table for RAM Model Solution (DT version)

Description

Returns a DT table summarizing the solution of a solved RAM model.

Usage

```
summary_ram(solution)
```

Arguments

solution	List returned by solve_ram().
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Value

DT datatable with optimal activity levels and objective value.

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